
D6.1 / Project branding and communication channels

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List of abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
PD	Parkinson's Disease
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

Deliverable D6.1 'Project branding and communication channels' delivers the AI-PROGNOSIS website and provides a detailed overview of the project's branding, online presence, communication material, and document templates.

It is the first deliverable of WP6 'Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation'. It falls under Task 6.1 'Dissemination and communication planning, implementation and monitoring', which focuses on planning, implementing, and monitoring the project's communication and dissemination activities.

The primary goal of this companion report is to introduce the coherent and recognisable visual identity image of the AI-PROGNOSIS project and to present the key communication channels and material for effective project communication.

1 Introduction

This document provides an overview of the AI-PROGNOSIS project's visual identity, website, social media channels, and communication kit. More specifically, the project's visual identity/brand (logo) with its unique features and a thorough summary of the project's website created for public engagement, communication, and outreach are introduced. The project's social media channels, communication tools and document templates are also presented.

1.1 Document scope

Deliverable D6.1 is the first deliverable of the WP6 'Dissemination, communication and exploitation' and is a component of Task 6.1 'Dissemination and communication planning, implementation and monitoring'. WP6 is an integral part of the AI-PROGNOSIS work plan and spans the entire duration of the project. Planning, conducting, and monitoring all the dissemination and communication activities of the project are the primary goals of Task 6.1. Part of its work is implementing the communication strategy, including creation and, where required, updating and maintenance of branding and other digital and printed media (e.g., website, social media, campaign material, press kits).

SMARTSOL SIA (SSOL) leads this task and is responsible for planning, implementing, monitoring, and coordinating activities. At the same time, the rest of the partners contribute to the plan, communication/dissemination activities, and reporting.

The project's website and all promotional material will be updated throughout the project's lifetime, displaying public information and the results of the project activities. Thus, D6.1 is related to all other tasks and deliverables of the project.

1.2 Document structure

The structure of this report is organised as follows:

- Executive summary: Provides an overview of the whole document.
- Introduction: Introduces the main scope of the deliverable, contributing tasks and relation to other project tasks.
- Project identity: Introduces the project's visual identity, including the logo and colour palette.
- Project website: Provides details about the AI-PROGNOSIS website, its purpose, structure, and functionalities.
- Social media: Identifies the project's presence on social media platforms, including LinkedIn, X (formerly Twitter), and Facebook, along with posting guidelines.
- Communication Kit and Templates: Introduces materials for print, digital assets like web banners, and documents and presentation templates for consistent project communication.
- Conclusions: Concludes the document and its key takeaways.

2 Project identity

The overall brand identity for AI-PROGNOSIS emerges from the harmonious union of several key elements, including:

- The minimalistic, yet distinctive logo mark;
- A standardised colour palette.

2.1 Logo

The AI-PROGNOSIS logo design in its standard usage format, is depicted in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1 The AI-PROGNOSIS logo

The logo is an easily recognisable visual identity of the project, which depicts the project's title combined with the colourful profile picture. The latter has reference to the multifaceted character of an implied tulip icon, the landmark representation of the Parkinson's Disease (PD)¹.

There are further variations (**Figure 2** and **Figure 3**) for use in different contrast contexts – i.e., for use against dark or multicoloured photorealistic backgrounds. None of these variants detract from the logo's spirit or meaning.

Figure 2 Monochromatic blue variation of the AI-PROGNOSIS logo

Figure 3 Monochromatic white variation of the AI-PROGNOSIS logo

¹Van der Wereld named his prized flower, the 'Dr. James Parkinson' tulip, to honor the English apothecary surgeon who originally described PD in 1812.

The AI-PROGNOSIS logo was designed to communicate several aspects of the project including project identity, title and distinctiveness in a visually attractive, unique, and recognisable form.

In keeping with the best-practice principles of logo design, it embodies the following attributes:

- simplified down to its core elements;
- utilises a moderate colour palette;
- minimises dependence on graphic embellishments like drop shadows;
- boasts a distinct and unique quality;
- achieves high levels of recognition and recall.

2.2 Colour palette

The project's colour palette corresponds with the colours featured in the project's logo and is consistently applied across AI-PROGNOSIS templates and dissemination materials (**Figure 4**).

Figure 4 The AI-PROGNOSIS colour palette

The primary purpose of establishing the colour palette for brand communications is to ensure a cohesive and distinct suite of messages that can be identified as originating from the brand.

3 Project website

The AI-PROGNOSIS website (www.ai-prognosis.eu) is the central place for online communications within the AI-PROGNOSIS project. At the same time, any additional digital/social media channels will strengthen the key messages from the project website.

3.1 The aim of the AI-PROGNOSIS website

The project's website aims to meet the following objectives throughout the lifetime of the AI-PROGNOSIS project and after it, i.e.:

- Present the AI-PROGNOSIS towards external stakeholders, sharing the main objectives of the project, describing the information related to the development, as well as the results and the barriers to overcome;
- Connect with additional interested stakeholders, which might lead to potential synergies and initiatives;
- Share information about the project's progress, the news from different dissemination activities, and public documents/deliverables;

- Provide access to the dissemination and communication material (“press kit”) for consortium partners and interested stakeholders, allowing the download of project material and documents.

The AI-PROGNOSIS website is designed to be visually attractive, engaging, easy to navigate, informative, relevant and timely. It is built flexibly; sections may be added or removed as required. It will be frequently updated with new input, e.g., project news, meetings, participation in events, developments, etc. The website also offers the option to download the dissemination material. Furthermore, social media accounts to be used by the consortium (Facebook, LinkedIn and X (formerly Twitter)), and project newsletters are also presented on the website. The information provided at the website portal results from all AI-PROGNOSIS project partners’ reviews and contributions, during August-September 2023.

Special attention was given to using positive language throughout the website's content. The content review was carried out by the project partner Uppsala University. The website went live on September 12, 2023.

3.2 Website structure and content

AI-PROGNOSIS website provides non-confidential project information, including project concept and methodology; consortium partners; core objectives; work packages; research and development overview; news and events.

The website structure is set up as follows (see also **Figure 5**):

- Home;
- About;
- Research & Development;
- Knowledge Base;
- Newsroom;
- Contact.

Figure 5 The AI-PROGNOSIS website structure

The **Home** page is dedicated to presenting the AI-PROGNOSIS project. It introduces the project's mission to advance PD diagnosis and care and highlights the significance of AI in healthcare (**Figure 6**).

The page highlights our motivation and provides a high-level summary of the project's research, methodological pillars and digital health ecosystem to be developed.

Furthermore, the Home page allows for an easy subscription to the project's Newsletters.

ai-prognosis Home About Research & Development Knowledge Base Newsroom Contact

Towards Parkinson's risk assessment and prognosis through AI

AI-PROGNOSIS is an Horizon Europe research and innovation project that aims to advance Parkinson's disease diagnosis and care through novel predictive models combined with digital biomarkers from everyday devices.

18 Partners from the EU and UK

4 Years in duration

3 Multi-center clinical studies

Our motivation

Parkinson's disease (PD) is the most common neurodegenerative movement disorder, affecting ~10 million people worldwide, and has no cure.

PD is often missed or misdiagnosed, as early symptoms are subtle and common with other diseases. Moreover, selecting the optimal medication regimen is usually a lengthy, "trial and error" process, leading to unnecessary suffering.

Our research

Based on multi-source sets of in-depth health and genetic data, AI-PROGNOSIS aims to develop and validate novel AI models for personalized Parkinson's disease (PD) risk assessment and prognosis.

- PD risk prediction**
Based on a person's relevant characteristics and early signs, measured also with everyday digital devices.
- PD progression prediction**
In terms of time to higher disability transition, with emphasis on motor impairment and known disease risk factors.
- Medication response prediction**
In terms of reduction of symptoms and of side effects, for a number of common dopaminergic treatments.

Our methodological pillars

- Co-creation**
Through continuous engagement with key stakeholders including persons with PD and healthcare professionals, during R&D.
- Trustworthy AI**
Compliance in practice with Trustworthy and Responsible AI guidelines, including the EU GDPR and the upcoming EU AI Act.
- Clinical validation**
Through well-designed, sufficiently-powered studies for proof-of-concept validation of research outcomes and digital tools.

Our envisioned AI tools

Ultimately, AI-PROGNOSIS aims to develop an ecosystem of digital health tools for persons with and without Parkinson's disease (PD) and healthcare professionals towards better disease screening and care. Driven by the novel AI models, these tools will offer personalized insights into disease risk, progression, and treatment, with the help of data from the smartphone and a smartwatch.

- mAI-Health app**
For persons with suspected PD to track their personalized risk.
- mAI-Care app**
For persons with PD to track symptoms, disease progression, and medication efficacy.
- mAI-Insights app**
Healthcare professionals' (HCP) app for PD screening, patient follow-up, and medication regimen optimization.

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Figure 6 The ai-prognosis.eu Home page

The **About** page of the AI-PROGNOSIS project's website encloses four subpages: The Project, Objectives, Work Packages, and Consortium.

The Project subpage (**Figure 7**) provides an overview of the AI-PROGNOSIS project vision, highlighting its innovative approach towards PD diagnosis and care using advanced AI technologies.

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Home About Research & Development Knowledge Base Newsroom Contact

The project

AI-PROGNOSIS - AI-based Parkinson's disease risk assessment and prognosis.

About Parkinson's disease

Parkinson's disease (PD) is the most common neurodegenerative movement disorder, affecting ~10 million people worldwide, and this number is projected to almost double by the year 2040.

PD is often missed or misdiagnosed, as early symptoms are subtle and common with other diseases. Effective, symptomatic treatments are available, yet selecting the optimal regimen is usually a lengthy, "trial and error" process, leading to unnecessary suffering. Overall costs to Europe have been estimated at ~€13.9 billion annually, with the cost per patient increasing with severity.

Our vision

With the AI-PROGNOSIS project, we aim to advance Parkinson's disease diagnosis and care through novel predictive models combined with digital biomarkers from everyday devices.

Our approach

Following a trustworthy and inclusive approach to AI development and through multidisciplinary expertise and broad stakeholder engagement, we will attempt to fulfill our vision by:

- Developing novel, predictive AI models for personalised PD risk assessment and prognosis (regarding disease progression and patients' response to medication) based on multi-source patient records and databases, including in-depth health, phenotypic and genetic data.
- Implementing a system of digital biomarkers informing the AI models by tracking key risk and progression markers, such as REM behaviour disorder and key motor symptoms, in daily living based on smartphone and wearable data.
- Translating the models and digital biomarkers into a validated, privacy-aware AI-driven toolkit, supporting healthcare professionals in disease screening, monitoring and treatment optimisation, via quantitative, explainable evidence, and offering individuals with/without PD tailored insights.

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Figure 7 The 'The Project' subpage

The Objectives subpage (**Figure 8**) outlines eight key objectives aimed at advancing PD research.

Figure 8 The 'Objectives' subpage

The Work Packages subpage (**Figure 9**) describes the six Work Packages (WPs) that contribute to the implementation of the AI-PROGNOSIS project.

Figure 9 The ‘Work packages’ subpage

The Consortium subpage (**Figure 10**) details all partners in the project that contribute to the overall success of the AI-PROGNOSIS project.

Figure 10 The 'Consortium' subpage

Overall, the About page, with its four subpages, provides a comprehensive overview of the AI-PROGNOSIS project, including its consortium, objectives, vision and approach with the ultimate goal of advancing PD diagnosis and care through innovative AI-driven methodologies.

The **Research & Development** page of the AI-PROGNOSIS project's website encloses three subpages: Research Overview, Clinical Studies, and Envisioned Tools.

The Research Overview subpage (**Figure 11**) provides information about the AI-PROGNOSIS research process, which includes data collection, development of predictive AI models, and the incorporation of digital biomarkers to improve the accuracy and effectiveness of personalised PD risk assessment, progression prediction, and medication response.

Home About Research & Development Knowledge Base Newsroom Contact

Our research

Leveraging multi-source datasets, including in-depth health and genetic data, at AI-PROGNOSIS, we will conduct research to develop and clinically validate novel, trustworthy AI models for personalised Parkinson's disease (PD) risk assessment and prognosis and combine them with digital biomarkers of risk and progression determinants from everyday devices.

Step 1 / Data

In AI-PROGNOSIS, we will amass and harmonise multi-source sets of in-depth health and genetic data labelled with incident PD diagnoses, disease progression history, or patients' response to medication.

Demographics, clinical scales, lifestyle data

Electrophysiological measurements and imaging data

Data from smartphones / wearables

SNPs and polygenic risk score

Step 2 / Predictive modelling

We will then analyse the harmonised datasets to develop robust, explainable, and overall trustworthy AI models predicting PD risk, progression, and medication response.

PD risk prediction

Based on a person's relevant characteristics and early signs, measured also with everyday digital devices.

PD progression prediction

In terms of time to higher disability transition, with emphasis on motor impairment and known disease milestones.

Medication response prediction

In terms of reduction of symptoms and of side effects, for a shortlist of common dopaminergic treatments.

Step 3 / Digital biomarkers

Digital biomarkers are health-related data collected by means of digital devices, such as smartphones and wearables. In AI-PROGNOSIS, we will develop new digital biomarkers of PD symptoms and along with existing ones, we will use them to inform the predictions of our predictive models.

Novel (developed in project)

REM Behaviour Disorder (RBD) Daytime somnolence

Existing (validated or with PoC)

Rest tremor Bradykinesia Rigidity Balance / posture Cognitive deficits Physical activity

Data comes first

Recent groundbreaking research efforts in the area of PD and beyond have created several relevant databases and biobanks with in-depth health and genetic data. We aim to leverage these data sources towards the development of our predictive models of PD risk, progression, and medication response.

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Figure 11 The 'Research Overview' subpage

The Clinical Studies subpage (**Figure 12**) presents AI-PROGNOSIS' clinical research. Particularly, the three clinical studies to be conducted in four different countries are outlined.

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Home About Research & Development Knowledge Base Newsroom Contact

Clinical studies

AI-PROGNOSIS will conduct three clinical studies in the EU and the UK. Study sites will attempt to recruit a diverse, inclusive participant cohort. Two studies are observational (dBM-DEV, AI-PRA) and one is a low-interventional study (AI-PMP).

01 Digital biomarkers development, validation and verification study (dBM-DEV study)

One of the objectives of the AI-PROGNOSIS project is to develop a system for objective tracking of key Parkinson's disease (PD) risk and progression markers in users' daily living. To this end, novel digital biomarkers (dBM) will be employed, derived from data generated by smartphone and smartwatch sensors. In the dBM-DEV study, new dBM will be developed and validated, while existing ones will be verified.

Objectives

The primary objective:

- to develop and validate dBM for REM sleep behaviour disorder (RBD).

The secondary objectives:

- to validate the dBM that will be developed to track daytime somnolence;
- to verify existing dBM for tracking bradykinesia, rigidity, rest tremor, dyskinesias, postural stability, and cognitive performance;
- to evaluate the performance of the dBM correcting for age and sex.

02 Artificial intelligence-based Parkinson's risk assessment study (AI-PRA study)

03 The AI-based Progression and Medication response Prediction (AI-PMP) study

Clinical studies will be conducted in 4 countries:

- Germany
- UK
- France
- Spain

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Figure 12 The 'Clinical studies' subpage

The Envisioned tools subpage (**Figure 13**) outlines the development of innovative tools by AI-PROGNOSIS.

Figure 13 The 'Envisioned tools' subpage

The **Knowledge Base** page (Figure 14) is a space to share the project's public deliverables, publications, and open datasets. Information will be posted as project outcomes are available.

Figure 14 The 'Knowledge base' page

The **Newsroom** page entails four subpages: News, Events, Newsletters and Communication kit.

The News (Figure 15) and Events subpages showcase the latest project updates and upcoming events, presented as distinct articles. The news pieces will be consistently updated and organised in chronological order. Meanwhile the Newsletter subpage will host a series of monthly project newsletters for download.

Figure 15 The 'News' subpage

The Communication kit subpage (**Figure 16**) is the central place for various dissemination and communication materials such as the logo, colour palette, flyer, poster and roll-up poster files, available for downloading.

Figure 16 The 'Communication kit' subpage

The **Contact page (Figure 17)** provides an easy way to contact the consortium and submit questions and queries.

Figure 17 The 'Contact' page

3.3 Website functionalities

In the first version of the AI-PRONGOSIS website, we focus on building the key features, while also considering possible future needs. At the current stage of the website development, the main available blocks of the website are:

- Subscriptions: Users are provided with the option to subscribe to newsletters, ensuring they stay updated with the latest project developments;
- Social media integration: Links to the project's social media accounts are included, promoting broader engagement and interaction with our audience;
- Contact information: A dedicated contact form allows users to reach out to our project team directly, fostering effective communication and collaboration;
- Responsive design: The website is designed to be accessible and functional on different devices, including desktops and smartphones (**Figure 18**);
- Downloads: Users can access and download project logos, dissemination materials, deliverables, publications, or partners' websites.

Figure 18 Adaptive website design: mobile views

The elements that could be incorporated into the development of the website at a later stage of the project are:

- Event Calendar: An events calendar from project events to related international workshops and conferences;
- Apps for the download: The inclusion of dedicated apps that will be developed with the project for download;
- Access to the Open datasets: Enabling access to open datasets will allow researchers to explore and analyse project data, ensuring openness and transparency.

This approach to website development ensures it can flexibly be adapted to new needs and requirements as the project moves forward.

4 Social media

4.1 Social media accounts

Dedicated X (formerly Twitter), LinkedIn, and Facebook social media profiles (**Table 1**) were created in July 2023 to strengthen the AI-PROGNOSIS communication efforts and to facilitate public engagement.

Table 1 AI-PROGNOSIS social media channels

Social media channel	AI-PROGNOSIS link in the channel
LinkedIn	@ai-prognosis
X (former Twitter)	@ai prognosis
Facebook	AI-PROGNOSIS

The accounts are linked with the AI-PROGNOSIS website and accessible by clicking on the corresponding Facebook, LinkedIn and X icons on the project's website.

4.2 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is the world's largest professional network on the internet². A LinkedIn profile (**Figure 19**) is a helpful tool for growing the network and establishing contacts with a targeted audience within the AI-PROGNOSIS. It will serve as space for disseminating project news, updates and achievements to increase outreach efforts and grow the follower's base.

Figure 19 The AI-PROGNOSIS LinkedIn profile

² <https://www.linkedin.com/help/linkedin/answer/a548441/what-is-linkedin-and-how-can-i-use-it-?lang=en-us&intendedLocale=en>

4.3 X (former Twitter)

X (former Twitter) is a social media platform where users can post and engage with short 280-character messages known as “tweets”³. The AI-PROGNOSIS X account (**Figure 20**) will serve as a dynamic platform to share moments from the project events, along with visual content that can effectively capture the essence of our achievements. Retweets will be used to endorse, emphasise and raise awareness of relevant messages.

Figure 20 The AI-PROGNOSIS X (former Twitter) profile

This approach aligns with the project’s objective to engage a larger audience and foster connections within the online community, increasing the visibility and impact of the project.

4.4 Facebook

The AI-PROGNOSIS Facebook account (**Figure 21**) will serve as a media platform to strengthen its communication and outreach efforts by disseminating project information, sharing project updates and visual content, promoting events, engaging with the target audience, and creating a digital presence that aligns with the project’s communication goals.

³The size of 280 characters could further been expanded up to 4000, under the [Twitter Blue's](#) paid subscription; this is not adopted by the AI-PROGNOSIS project.

Figure 21 The AI-PROGNOSIS Facebook profile

4.5 Social media posting guidelines

Guidelines and principles for the consortium to take into account when posting on social media, i.e.:

- Never post pictures or text containing confidential information from the consortium's internal meetings;
- Always use appropriate, inoffensive language (to ensure we get responses and stimulate debate), examples include:
 - If possible, use "people first language", meaning "person with Parkinson's disease" rather than "Parkinson's patient".
- Always be receptive to our readers' arguments – if we disagree, we can defend our position with politeness;
- Gain/maintain credibility by sharing worthwhile, relevant content and showing respect for other cultures and ideas online as well as offline;
- Always be aware that libel and defamation laws apply;

- Use the project handle consistently throughout the overall project implementation;
- Regularly communicate information about our project, especially if you have a strong, well established social media presence;
- Use handles, such as @HorizonEU and @EUfunded, in our tweets (posts on X) and LinkedIn posts to maximise visibility and be recognised as part of the Horizon Europe community;
- Post pictures, videos or data visualisations to spark interest, taking into account how social media is becoming increasingly visual;
- Share images and tag other X (formerly Twitter) and LinkedIn accounts to build a relationship with the audience and make them aware (the account tagged receives a notification) of content that might interest them in the hope that they might want to reshare it.

5 Communication kit and templates

5.1 Material for print

At the beginning of the project, in months 1-3, a communication kit was developed, including a project poster, flyer and roll-up banner. These items reflect the project's brand and provide an overview of the essential information about the project. The stakeholders and interested parties can easily access and download these materials from the project's website for promotion or representation purposes of the project.

The project **flyer/poster** introduces AI-PROGNOSIS, as Horizon Europe research and innovation endeavour and provides a brief overview of the project. It incorporates the project logo, profile picture and a colour palette, fostering a unified project brand identity.

The project flyer/poster (**Figure 22**) will be used in various contexts to promote and raise awareness about the AI-PROGNOSIS project, including conferences, workshops, various events and presentations.

Parkinson's is the most common neurodegenerative movement disorder, with subtle early symptoms and no cure, affecting ~10 million people worldwide.

AI-PROGNOSIS is an Horizon Europe research and innovation project aiming to advance Parkinson's diagnosis and care through novel predictive models of risk, progression, and medication response, combined with digital biomarkers from everyday smart devices.

Learn more on ai-prognosis.eu

[in](#) @ai-prognosis [X](#) @aiprognois [f](#) AI-PROGNOSIS

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Figure 22 The AI-PROGNOSIS Poster/flyer

The AI-PROGNOSIS **roll-up banner (Figure 23)** serves as a supplementary communication tool alongside project poster and flyer.

A roll-up banner is designed to be freestanding and can be easily set up and displayed in various settings. A roll-up banner will be used as a promotional and informative tool at events, conferences, exhibitions, workshops, and other public events. The large size of a roll-up banner provides visual impact, making it noticeable from a distance.

Figure 23 The AI-PROGNOSIS Roll-up banner

The communication kit is currently available in English. However, the project consortium is aware that translations into additional languages may become necessary to reach the broader audience as the project progresses.

5.2 Digital material (Web banners)

Dedicated banners (**Figure 24**, **Figure 25**, **Figure 26**) have been designed for all AI-PROGNOSIS social media profiles to ensure a solid appearance. The banners incorporate the project's colour palette, ensuring visual consistency with the overall brand style. Design harmony across all platforms ensures a professional project presentation and promotes effective engagement with the target audience.

Figure 24 LinkedIn web banner

Figure 25 X (former Twitter) web banner

Figure 26 Facebook web banner

5.3 Document and presentation templates

Three essential templates, i.e.: Deliverable, Meeting Minutes and Presentation templates were designed to enhance the project management, reporting and communication within the consortium and maintain consistency in the project's deliverables, meeting documentation, and presentations.

The Deliverable template (Figure 27) is a standardised document format for delivering and documenting project deliverables. It includes several sections and details on the deliverable, contributors, the history of the document, its contents, and references. The template's purpose is to preserve consistency and offer a uniform structure for reporting on project deliverables.

D## / Deliverable title in sentence case

Editor Person full name (PARTNER SHORT NAME)	Contractual delivery Month YYYY	Actual delivery Month YYYY
Deliverable type [R - Document, report] or [DMP - Data Management Plan] or [DEM - Demonstrator, pilot, prototype] or [DEC - Websites, patent filings, videos, etc] or [OTHER]	Dissemination level [PU – Public] or [SEN – Sensitive]	Version - date ## - DD/MM/YYYY

Deliverable ID	
Project acronym	AI-PROGNOSIS
Project full title	Artificial intelligence-based Parkinson's disease risk assessment and prognosis
Grant Agreement ID	101080581
Deliverable number	D##
Deliverable title	Deliverable title in sentence case
Work package	WP# - WP title in sentence case
Deliverable type	[R - Document, report] or [DMP - Data Management Plan] or [DEM - Demonstrator, pilot, prototype] or [DEC - Websites, patent filings, videos, etc] or [OTHER]
Dissemination level	[PU – Public] or [SEN – Sensitive]
Version - date	## - DD/MM/YYYY
Contractual delivery	Month YYYY
Actual delivery	Month YYYY
Lead partner	PARTNER SHORT NAME
Editor	Person Full Name (PARTNER SHORT NAME)
Contributors	Person 1 Full Name (PARTNER SHORT NAME); Person 2 Full Name (PARTNER SHORT NAME); ...
Reviewed by	Full name of Reviewer 1 (PARTNER SHORT NAME) Full name of Reviewer 2 (PARTNER SHORT NAME)
Approved by	Leontios Hadjileontidis (AUTH, Project Coordinator)
Keywords	In alphabetical order A keyword; B keyword; ...

Figure 27 The AI-PROGNOSIS Deliverable template

The **Meeting minutes** template (Figure 28) is dedicated to documenting meeting minutes and making written records that capture the key discussions, decisions, and action items. This template provides a standardised format for recording information during various meetings, such as plenary meetings, work package meetings, or meetings with specific titles.

Meeting minutes

[Plenary meeting #] or [WP# meeting ##] or [Title of meeting]		
Date(s)	Place	Organiser(s)
DD Month YYYY	[City, Country] or [Online]	PARTNER SHORT NAME
Version - date	Dissemination level	
## - DD/MM/YYYY	SEN – Sensitive	

Document¹ history

Version	Date	Minute contributors	Action / status
1.0	DD/MM/YYYY	PARTNER SHORT NAME 1; PARTNER SHORT NAME 2; ...	Initial version of minutes
...			
2.0	DD/MM/YYYY	PARTNER SHORT NAME 1; PARTNER SHORT NAME 2; ...	Approved minutes

Contents

1 Attendees	2
2 Agenda	2
3 Minutes	2
3.1 Agenda item 1	2
3.2 Agenda item 2	3
3.3	3

1 Attendees

Full name	Partner	Notes
...	...	E.g. Left the meeting before Agenda item 2
...	...	
...	...	

2 Agenda

- Agenda item 1
- Agenda item 2
- ...

3 Minutes

3.1 Agenda item 1

Statements

- ...
- ...

Or write 'None'

Decisions

- ...
- ...

Or write 'None'

Action items

A#	Description	Responsible	Due date
A#	Action item short description ...	PARTNER	DD/MM/YYYY
A#	...		

Or delete table and write 'None'

Notes

Any notes go here or write 'None'

Figure 28 The AI-PROGNOSIS Meeting minutes template

The **Presentation** template (Figure 29) is designed for project meetings or events and provides a structured format for communicating key achievements, addressing delays,

showcasing progress on specific tasks, and outlining the next steps. It is intended to ensure that the project-related presentations cover essential information clearly and organised.

Figure 29 The AI-PROGNOSIS Presentation template

6 Conclusions

The D6.1 lays the foundation for the communication and dissemination activities of the AI-PROGNOSIS project, emphasising the importance of a solid and unified visual identity, a user-friendly website, active social media engagement, and a defined set of principles. The AI-PROGNOSIS logo underpins the project's visual identity, ensuring the project is easily recognisable.

The AI-PROGNOSIS website and social media channels are effective tools supporting the project's communication and dissemination activities. They provide informative content and regular updates, which raises engagement with the project's target audience. Clear language guidelines ensure the consortium communicates professionally and respects the audience's opinions.

In addition, the communication kit, including a poster, flyer, and roll-up banner, strengthens the project's brand identity and is easily accessible for dissemination and communication purposes. Document and presentation templates ensure consistency in the consortium's project reporting and communication.

In conclusion, the AI-PROGNOSIS logo, website, and social media profiles are the strong foundation of the project and are essential to reaching our target audience and achieving the project's overall communication and dissemination goals.